

DEFORMATION OF GRAPHENE OXIDE: FROM MODEL TO BULK NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Graphene oxide (GO) has been prepared from graphite, and deposited onto poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) substrate, where the mono- and multi-layer GO have been identified using AFM. Raman spectroscopy was used to monitor their deformation and it was found the Raman D band position (ω_D) downshifts as the GO is stretched, similar to the observation on graphene. The Raman D band shift rate was further used to estimate the effective Young's modulus of both the mono- and multi-layer GO.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to its high surface area, high strength as well as its multifunctionality, graphene is clearly a strong candidate for a nano-filler in polymer based nanocomposites [1]. However, it is difficult to disperse it homogeneously in a polymer matrix as a result of its chemically inert surface. One alternative is to use its derivative, GO, because of the presence of functional groups that promote its dispersion in a matrix [2]. Nevertheless, the Young's modulus of monolayer GO, approximately 200~250 GPa [3], is only about 1/5~1/4 of that of monolayer graphene, possibly due to the structural distortion as a result of oxidation and defects. GO also has twice the thickness of graphene [4].

The mechanics of graphene in the nanocomposites has been studied extensively [1] but an efficient way of monitoring the deformation mechanics of GO in nanocomposite is still needed [2, 5, 6]. In this work, the deformation of the model monolayer and multilayer GO nanocomposites has been followed using Raman spectroscopy. Based upon the rate of shift of the Raman D band with strain ($d\omega_D/d\varepsilon$), the effective Young's modulus ($E_{\text{eff}}(\text{GO})$) of the GO can be estimated. This work presents a fundamental and general method to estimate the mechanical properties of GO in nanocomposites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and sample preparation

The graphite (Grade 2369) was supplied by Graphexel Ltd. All other reagents were of analytical grade and used without further purification. The GO was prepared using the modified Hummers method [7, 8], and details can be found in Ref. [9]. Finally, the GO was dispersed in water and deposited onto PMMA beam and SiO₂ substrate followed by drying under ambient condition, for Raman spectroscopy and scanning electron microscope (SEM), respectively. The GO solution used for casting was diluted to avoid the possible re-aggregation of GO flakes during the water evaporation.

2.2 Characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was carried out on dried GO powder using an X'Pert DY609 X-Ray diffractometer (Philips) with a Cu K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.542\text{\AA}$). Atomic force microscope (AFM) images were obtained using a Dimension 3100 AFM (Bruker) in the tapping mode. SEM images were obtained using a Philips XL30 FEGSEM.

Raman spectra were obtained using Renishaw 1000/2000 spectrometers equipped with HeNe lasers ($\lambda = 633\text{ nm}$) with a laser spot size around 1~2 μm . The incident laser polarization was parallel to the

strain while the scattered radiation was randomly polarized. The specimens were deformed in a four-point bending rig, and the strain was measured by a strain gauge. The Raman bands were fitted using a Lorentzian function [10].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Microstructure of the GO flakes

Figure 1: XRD pattern of the dried GO powder.

As shown in the XRD pattern in Fig. 1, there is a characteristic peak of GO at $2\theta = 10.5^\circ$. This corresponds to an interlayer spacing of 0.84 nm, and the expansion of the interlayer spacing from the value of 0.34 nm for graphene indicates the presence of oxygen functional groups and defects after oxidation [5].

It is shown in Fig. 2(a) the SEM images of the GO flakes deposited onto SiO_2 substrate, with irregular geometries. Their size as large as over 50 μm can be found but it is broadly distributed with an average value of $\sim 14.85 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 2(b)). Generally the GO flakes are quite flat, however a few crumples still occur, possibly during the evaporation of the solvent [11].

Figure 2: (a) SEM image and (b) lateral dimension distribution of the GO flakes.

3.2 Deformation of monolayer and multilayer GO

Fig. 3(a)(b) are the AFM images of two typical GO flakes. It can be seen from that both GO flakes are of large lateral dimensions over 15 μm that ensures effective stress transfer from the substrate from the knowledge of graphene [12]. The height profiles in Fig. 3(c)(d), corresponding to the lines in Fig. 3(a)(b) indicate the GO in (a) and (b) is monolayer and multilayer, with a thickness of $\sim 1.5 \text{ nm}$ and $\sim 40 \text{ nm}$, respectively.

Figure 3: AFM images of (a) monolayer and (b) multilayer GO. The height profiles in (c) and (d) correspond to the lines in (a) and (b), respectively. (The spots on the images correspond to the positions where the Raman spectra were subsequently obtained.)

The Raman spectra were obtained from these two flakes (Fig. 4). They are essentially the same, but due to the extra small thickness, the Raman scattering intensity of monolayer GO is much weaker than the one from multilayer GO thus the Raman spectrum is quite scattered. However, the Raman D band and G band can still be resolved from these two Raman spectra.

Figure 4: Raman spectra of (a) monolayer and (b) multilayer GO. (The positions of the Raman D and G bands are also indicated.)

A single Lorentzian peak was used for the curve fitting of the Raman D band in both situations. Fig. 5 shows the ω_D as the function of tensile strain ϵ for these two specimens. For the monolayer GO

(Fig. 5(a)), when it was stretched to a strain of 0.4%, ω_D , recorded at the central region (Fig. 3(a)) [12], was found to downshift with a $d\omega_D/d\varepsilon = -9.9 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$, as a result of the stretching of the C-C bonds [13] due to the stress transfer from the substrate to GO. For the multilayer GO, a same downshift behavior of ω_D was found and the similar $d\omega_D/d\varepsilon$ indicates the stretching of GO in those two specimens is similar.

Figure 5: ω_D as the function of strain ε for (a) monolayer and (b) multilayer GO. The positions where the tests were undertaken are indicated as spots in Fig.3.

3.3 Deformation mechanics of GO

It is reported all of the Raman D, G and 2D bands downshift as graphene is stretched that can be understood as a result of the elongation of the C-C bonds [13] using the knowledge of Grüneisen parameter [14]. The Grüneisen parameter of the Raman D band γ_D , is given as [14]:

$$\left(\frac{d\omega_D}{d\varepsilon} \right)_{\text{Ref}} = -\omega_D^0 \gamma_D (1-\nu) \quad (1)$$

where ω_D^0 is ω_D at zero strain, and ν is either the Poisson's ratio of the substrate in this study or of the graphene itself if for freestanding graphene. If γ_D is taken as a value of 3.55 from graphene [14], and $\nu = 0.35$ [15] for the PMMA substrate used here, the reference $d\omega_D/d\varepsilon$ ($(d\omega_D/d\varepsilon)_{\text{Ref}}$) can be calculated as $\sim -30 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain. The $d\omega_D/d\varepsilon$ for both of the specimens in this work is $\sim -10 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$, only $\sim 1/3$ of the reference value, the possible reasons will be discussed later.

The Young's modulus of monolayer GO was measured as 200~250 GPa [3], about 1/5~1/4 of that of monolayer graphene. Paci et al. [4] carried out a theoretical calculation, showing a decrease of the modulus by a factor of ~ 2 when the monolayer graphene is oxidized to GO because of the doubled thickness than its original, and it was further halved by the introduction of defect and also the oxygen functional groups. Provided the massive defects and oxygen functional groups in GO, it was revealed recently that the real structure of GO still contains a graphitic-similar plane but decorated with a number of debris [16].

It has been well established that the rate of Raman band shift per unit strain for different forms of graphitic carbon can be related to the effective Young's modulus of the materials [17, 18]. For GO, it will be instructive to see, how the Raman D band shift can be correlated to its mechanical properties, thus to evaluate the effective level of reinforcement. As demonstrated above the presence of defects in GO reduces its Young's modulus by a factor of 2 [4], and also considering the relatively intact graphitic plane of GO [16], it is proposed that this structural distortion will lead to a halved $d\omega_D/d\varepsilon$ of GO compared to that of graphene. Consequently, the effective modulus of GO ($E_{\text{eff}}(\text{GO})$) in the nanocomposites can be given as [9]:

$$E_{\text{eff}}(\text{GO}) = \frac{d\omega_{\text{D}}/d\varepsilon}{(d\omega_{\text{D}}/d\varepsilon)_{\text{Ref}}} \times \frac{t_{\text{gra}}}{t_{\text{GO}}} \times E_{\text{gra}} \quad (2)$$

where $(d\omega_{\text{D}}/d\varepsilon)_{\text{Ref}}$ is used as ($\sim -30 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ as derived above [14] for the supported graphene on the same PMMA substrate, E_{gra} denote the Young's modulus of graphene, which is 1050 GPa [19]. t_{gra} and t_{GO} represent the thickness of monolayer graphene (0.34 nm [19]) and GO (0.84 nm [9]), respectively, to take into account the effect of the thickness on the Young's modulus [4].

Substituting the experimental $d\omega_{\text{D}}/d\varepsilon$ value into Eq. 2, an $E_{\text{eff}}(\text{GO})$ can be obtained as ~ 140 GPa for both the monolayer and multilayer GO. This is in contrast to what has been observed on graphene [20], where the effective Young's modulus actually drops down from mono- to multi-layer graphene. This result possibly suggests a much better interlayer stress transfer of GO than that of graphene. Even though, the corresponding $E_{\text{eff}}(\text{GO}) \sim 140$ GPa is still lower than the Young's modulus of monolayer GO [3]. This difference can be interpreted as the absence of direct bonding between the GO flake and the PMMA substrate, because the model GO nanocomposites is prepared simply by depositing the GO suspension onto the PMMA substrate without any further chemical treatment.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Different GO flakes have been identified using AFM, with their thickness corresponding to mono- and multi-layer structures. It was found that the ω_{D} band downshifts as the GO was under tensile strain, similar to the observations on graphene. However, in contrast, it was found that both GO flakes exhibited similar $d\omega_{\text{D}}/d\varepsilon$. A correlation was further established to estimate the effective Young's modulus of GO with the $d\omega_{\text{D}}/d\varepsilon$, using the knowledge of Grüneisen parameter. The similar Young's modulus of the mono- and multi-layer GO, calculated from $d\omega_{\text{D}}/d\varepsilon$, imply a higher internal stress transfer efficiency within GO than in the case of graphene.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R.J. Young, I.A. Kinloch, L. Gong and K.S. Novoselov, The mechanics of graphene nanocomposites: a review, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2012, pp. 1459-1476 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.05.005).
- [2] D.A. Dikin, S. Stankovich, E.J. Zimney, R.D. Piner, G.H.B. Dommett, G. Evmenenko, S.T. Nguyen and R.S. Ruoff, Preparation and characterization of graphene oxide paper, *Nature*, **448**, 2007, pp. 457-460 (doi: 10.1038/nature06016).
- [3] J.W. Suk, R.D. Piner, J. An and R.S. Ruoff, Mechanical properties of monolayer graphene oxide, *ACS Nano*, **4**, 2010, pp. 6557-6564 (doi: 10.1021/nn101781v).
- [4] J.T. Paci, T. Belytschko and G.C. Schatz, Computational studies of the structure, behavior upon heating, and mechanical properties of graphite oxide, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, **111**, 2007, pp. 18099-18111 (doi: 10.1021/jp075799g).
- [5] Y. Xu, W. Hong, H. Bai, C. Li and G. Shi, Strong and ductile poly(vinyl alcohol)/graphene oxide composite films with a layered structure, *Carbon*, **47**, 2009, pp. 3538-3543 (doi: 10.1016/j.carbon.2009.08.022).
- [6] Y. Gao, L.-Q. Liu, S.-Z. Zu, K. Peng, D. Zhou, B.-H. Han and Z. Zhang, The effect of interlayer adhesion on the mechanical behaviors of macroscopic graphene oxide papers, *ACS Nano*, **5**, 2011, pp. 2134-2141 (doi: 10.1021/nn103331x).
- [7] W.S. Hummers and R.E. Offeman, Preparation of graphitic oxide, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **80**, 1958, pp. 1339-1339 (doi: 10.1021/ja01539a017).

- [8] Y. Xu, K. Sheng, C. Li and G. Shi, Self-assembled graphene hydrogel via a one-step hydrothermal process, *ACS Nano*, **4**, 2010, pp. 4324-4330 (doi: 10.1021/nn101187z).
- [9] Z. Li, R.J. Young and I.A. Kinloch, Interfacial stress transfer in graphene oxide nanocomposites, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, **5**, 2013, pp. 456-463 (doi: 10.1021/am302581e).
- [10] L. Deng, S.J. Eichhorn, C.-C. Kao and R.J. Young, The effective young's modulus of carbon nanotubes in composites, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, **3**, 2011, pp. 433-440 (doi: 10.1021/am1010145).
- [11] X. Ma, M.R. Zachariah and C.D. Zangmeister, Crumpled nanopaper from graphene oxide, *Nano Letters*, **12**, 2012, pp. 486-489 (doi: 10.1021/nl203964z).
- [12] L. Gong, I.A. Kinloch, R.J. Young, I. Riaz, R. Jalil and K.S. Novoselov, Interfacial stress transfer in a graphene monolayer nanocomposite, *Advanced Materials*, **22**, 2010, pp. 2694-2697 (doi: 10.1002/adma.200904264).
- [13] S.B. Cronin, A.K. Swan, M.S. Ünlü, B.B. Goldberg, M.S. Dresselhaus and M. Tinkham, Measuring the uniaxial strain of individual single-wall carbon nanotubes: Resonance Raman spectra of atomic-force-microscope modified single-wall nanotubes, *Physical Review Letters*, **93**, 2004, pp. 167401 (doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.93.167401).
- [14] T.M.G. Mohiuddin, A. Lombardo, R.R. Nair, A. Bonetti, G. Savini, R. Jalil, N. Bonini, D.M. Basko, C. Galiotis, N. Marzari, K.S. Novoselov, A.K. Geim and A.C. Ferrari, Uniaxial strain in graphene by Raman spectroscopy: G peak splitting, Grüneisen parameters, and sample orientation, *Physical Review B*, **79**, 2009, pp. 205433 (doi: 10.1103/PhysRevB.79.205433).
- [15] K.N. Kudin, G.E. Scuseria and B.I. Yakobson, C₂f, BN, and C nanoshell elasticity from *ab initio* computations, *Physical Review B*, **64**, 2001, pp. 235406 (doi: 10.1103/PhysRevB.64.235406).
- [16] J.P. Rourke, P.A. Pandey, J.J. Moore, M. Bates, I.A. Kinloch, R.J. Young and N.R. Wilson, The real graphene oxide revealed: stripping the oxidative debris from the graphene-like sheets, *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, **50**, 2011, pp. 3173-3177 (doi: 10.1002/anie.201007520).
- [17] C.A. Cooper, R.J. Young and M. Halsall, Investigation into the deformation of carbon nanotubes and their composites through the use of Raman spectroscopy, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **32**, 2001, pp. 401-411 (doi: 10.1016/s1359-835x(00)00107-x).
- [18] O. Frank, G. Tsoukleri, I. Riaz, K. Papagelis, J. Parthenios, A.C. Ferrari, A.K. Geim, K.S. Novoselov and C. Galiotis, Development of a universal stress sensor for graphene and carbon fibres, *Nature Communications*, **2**, 2011, pp. 255 (doi: 10.1038/ncomms1247).
- [19] C. Lee, X. Wei, J.W. Kysar and J. Hone, Measurement of the elastic properties and intrinsic strength of monolayer graphene, *Science*, **321**, 2008, pp. 385-388 (doi: 10.1126/science.1157996).
- [20] L. Gong, R.J. Young, I.A. Kinloch, I. Riaz, R. Jalil and K.S. Novoselov, Optimizing the reinforcement of polymer-based nanocomposites by graphene, *ACS Nano*, **6**, 2012, pp. 2086-2095 (doi: 10.1021/nn203917d).